

From (Micro-) Circularity To (Macro-) Mitigation: A Framework Bridging Firm-Level Circularity, Rebound Effects and Policies

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Abstract

Within firms, circular economy practices aimed at reducing, reusing, and recycling resources have the potential to improve resource efficiency. Yet, these micro-level interventions may not necessarily result in economy-wide reductions in resource consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. This paper presents a novel analytical framework to examine the pathways through which firm-level circularity leads to a "macro-level circular economy" characterized by lower resource use, extraction, and disposal, and ultimately, lower greenhouse gas emissions. Drawing from several strands of literature and employing sequential reasoning, we identify the necessary conditions under which circular practices at the firm level generate tangible benefits at the aggregate level. We show that these conditions correspond closely to principles of sufficiency. Subsequently, we examine policy instruments that can facilitate the achievement of a macro circular economy.

Key Words: *Circular Economy, Rebound Effect, Climate Mitigation*

JEL Classification: *Q53, Q54*

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1 Introduction

Circular economy practices—which aim to reduce, reuse, and recycle resources at the firm level—have the potential to increase resource efficiency and are expected to play a significant role in achieving net zero emissions and avoiding major climate risks (IPCC, 2022). Europe is at the forefront of this debate, with a recent strong push towards circular economy practices to reduce resource consumption while addressing climate change (Communication 2020/18, 2021; CEAP, 2021). Yet, the implications of firm-level circular practices for aggregate resource use and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are unclear. Studies like Material Economics (2019, 2020); Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2021); Gallego-Schmid et al. (2020) and Mostert et al. (2021) indicate varying resource and emission saving potentials depending on the sector, with circular strategies in the industry, energy, and transport sectors being the most promising ones. However, most studies typically assume rather than provide decisive proof of the mitigation potentials connected to specific circular economy strategies (Cantzler et al., 2020).

There are at least three main reasons why the implementation of circular practices and business models by firms might fall short of expectations and not translate into lower overall demand for resources (materials and energy) and associated greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. First, the "rebound effect" literature shows that efficiency gains may not fully translate into lower consumption (Greening et al., 2000; Gillingham et al., 2013, 2016; Font Vivanco et al., 2016; Zink and Geyer, 2017; Skelton et al., 2020; Chenavaz et al., 2021; Castro et al., 2022), and can even increase consumption through a "backfire" effect (Saunders, 2000; Brookes, 2000; Druckman et al., 2011; Chenavaz et al., 2021).¹ These studies generally focus on the energy context, but similar dynamics potentially characterize the use of material. Second, certain circular practices can increase the quantity of material available in the market. This is the case, for instance, when recycled materials or goods that would otherwise be discarded are reintroduced into the market (Zink and Geyer, 2017).² Third, thermodynamic limits suggest that circular systems consume

¹According to Zink and Geyer (2017), the rebound effect in circular economy occurs when activities, which aim to reduce per-unit production impact, have the unintended consequence of increasing the production levels, thereby diminishing their overall benefits. Our paper builds upon and extends the rebound literature, but does not assume that circular activities are inherently less resource-intensive. Instead, this has to be demonstrated in what we call "the resource counterpart" (Section 3.3)

²This mechanism may be characterized as a rebound effect if recycled materials were intended as lower-impact production inputs to replace virgin materials in the production process. It should be noted, however, that many recycling and reuse initiatives do not originate from considerations within

resources and produce waste, meaning that strategies like recycling and reuse may still contribute to resource depletion in a significant way (Korhonen et al., 2018).

We develop a novel framework that allows us to jointly identify and synthesize all conditions under which *firm-level circular practices* translate into what we call a *macro-level circular economy*. This is a situation characterized by lower resource use, extraction, and disposal —and ultimately, climate change mitigation. Figure 1 illustrates the main components of our framework, which is built using sequential reasoning. First, we identify the channels that connect firm-level *circular strategies* to aggregate resource use and discuss the conditions that guarantee *resource mitigation* (Figure 1), i.e., the reduction in resource used, whether virgin or recycled.³ According to our framework, the impact of firm-level circular practices on economy-wide resource savings is mediated by three channels, which we term "counterparts". We use this term to highlight both the transmission pathways and the resulting effects of circular actions. We identify (i) the "financial counterpart", namely how circular practices affect firms' costs, pricing, and spending, all the way to downstream demand; (ii) the "material counterpart", namely how circular practices influence firms' demand and supply of materials directly (e.g., an increased supply of materials via recycling) and (iii) a "resource counterpart", namely how circular practices affect demand for materials and energy indirectly (e.g., infrastructure needs and digital support). In all these counterparts, we discuss the important role of substitution effects. Second, we characterize the connections between resource mitigation, *reduced disposal* and *reduced extraction*. Third, we identify the specific conditions that guarantee that firm-level circularity practices translate to macro-level resource savings and discuss the policy levers that aim to achieve resource mitigation. Lastly, we discuss the synergies with lower greenhouse gas emissions, i.e., *climate mitigation*.

Our contribution to the literature is threefold. First, while qualitative in nature, our framework enables the joint exploration of the various channels through which micro-level circularity translates to macro-level resource savings. It thus fills an important research gap. Results on the extent to which circular practices result in firm-level or economy-wide resource savings are currently disconnected and scattered across at least three different streams of literature - the economic and sustainability literature on rebound effects (Greening et al., 2000; Gillingham et al., 2013; Figge et al., 2014; Gillingham et al., 2016; Font Vivanco et al., 2016; Zink and Geyer, 2017; Skelton et al., 2020; Chenavaz et al., 2021; Castro et al., 2022; Metić and Pigosso, 2022; Heun et al., 2025); the management

the production process itself, but rather emerge as measures to prevent resource wastage and directly increase material availability at the society-level.

³We mainly focus on resource mitigation, encompassing both virgin and recycled resources, though CE is often framed around reducing virgin extraction. Our choice is motivated by the fact that meeting environmental challenges requires decreasing the economy's total material and energy footprint (Korhonen et al., 2018). Recycling processes carry environmental impacts and cannot preserve resource stocks under growth exceeding 1% (Grosse, 2014). Moreover, resource flows cannot grow continuously through recycling alone while virgin material use declines.

Figure 1: Paper outlook

literature describing the circular strategies and circular business models (Bocken et al., 2016; Nußholz, 2017; Geissdoerfer et al., 2020); and the industrial ecology literature on material flows, material footprints and life cycle assessment (Cantzler et al., 2020; Haas et al., 2020; Mostert et al., 2021; Desing et al., 2021). This limits the ability to inform policy decisions.

Second, our framework informs and guides both researchers and policymakers. Researchers in engineering and material modeling of circularity can build on our results to enhance the modeling of circularity and clarify the primary hypotheses underlying model results. Many existing models generally abstract from market features or do not explore the sensitivity of their results to changes in economic assumptions (Pauliuk et al., 2017; McCarthy et al., 2018). We contribute to the policy debate by highlighting the need for a policy portfolio that can support the translation of micro-circularity into macro-mitigation. Such a portfolio complements policies promoting circular practices of firms with interventions that limit extraction through biodiversity programs, taxes, and standards, while promoting consumer sufficiency.

Third, the framework offers a key policy and research insight, namely that a macro circular economy —one that achieves reduced resource consumption in line with planetary boundaries— is closely tied to the concept of sufficiency. While circular economy and sufficiency concepts are often considered in isolation (Figge and Thorpe, 2023), we show that avoiding circular economy rebound effects is crucially conditional on strong environmental preferences, e.g., commitments from consumers, firms, and governments to low-resource activities and environmental preservation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the key assumptions of our framework. Section 3 examines the various pathways from micro circular practices to macro resource use, disposal, and extraction. Section 4 identifies the conditions and policy levers that help achieve a macro circular economy. Section 5 discusses how our insights help identify the mechanisms through which a macro-level circular economy can contribute to climate mitigation and illustrates fruitful avenues of future research. Section 6 concludes.

2 Key Concepts and Assumptions

Our focus is on how circular practices affect the absolute variation in aggregate flows of resources used, extracted, and disposed of.⁴ Hence, our starting point is the circular behavior of firms, i.e., their implementation of circular practices targeting material use. Circular practices are typically mapped into a hierarchical order through the "R frameworks" (the 3Rs-Reduction, Reuse, Recycle (Ghisellini et al., 2016) or the 10Rs - Refuse, Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, and Recover (Potting et al., 2017; Kirchherr et al., 2017)). We exclude the last R (recovery) from our analysis, as it targets energy.⁵ Firms' circular behavior can simultaneously affect the type of input (e.g., use of recycled materials or used products), the production process (e.g., sharing business model), or the output offered to consumers (e.g., thinner packaging). While we exclude practices such as recovery, which target energy efficiency, we account for the impact that changes in material use may have on energy consumption. In our framework, "circular products" encompass all intermediate products (including materials) and final products that possess circular characteristics based on the 10R framework — such as shared products, lighter-weight designs, or recycled components. "Secondary products" are a subset of circular products, referring specifically to items that were destined for disposal but have been diverted for reuse or recycling instead. We consider practices that introduce circular products with various potentials to replace non-circular alternatives, from low to high. Lastly, we examine the effects of companies implementing new circular strategies versus having no circular strategy. This is tantamount to conceptualizing an exogenous shock in which circular strategies become profitable for a significant number of firms due to factors such as technological advancements or shifting consumer

⁴Flows are observed within a given period (e.g., a year).

⁵"Recover" is defined as energy recovery from incineration or by anaerobic digestion by Potting et al. (2017). The available R-lists (Potting et al., 2017) establish a *de facto* priority order based on the waste treatment hierarchy, whereby strategies higher in the hierarchy, such as "refuse", e.g., bulk selling, are considered more effective in managing waste than strategies lower in the hierarchy, such as "recycle". However, the basis of the waste hierarchy for such ranking is not strictly rigorous (Rasmussen and Vigsoe, 2005). This is illustrated by the fact that in the case of waste management, the EU Waste Directive recommends checking the environmental outcome of the hierarchy with life-cycle analyses.

preferences. We analyze the short- to medium-term consequences of this shock on the variation in resource use at the macro level.⁶

Understanding under which conditions micro-level circular practices translate to macro-level circularity requires simplifying assumptions regarding both the supply and demand sides of the economy. We summarize the key assumptions here and refer the reader to Appendix A for further details.

Our key assumption regarding the supply side is that firms are profit-maximizing. We focus on the case where firms choose to implement circular strategies when they result in the same or a higher profit than business as usual.⁷ This implies that firms operate in an environment which allows them to maintain or increase their profitability, e.g., through incremental innovation and knowledge supporting circular practices or the increased presence of supply and demand for circular products (Galarrraga Gallastegui, 2002; Boyer et al., 2021). Firms operate in a setting in which the technological frontier is relatively stable and they are not confronted with radical or breakthrough circular innovation. Firms cannot influence the market price of the products or services they buy in upstream markets, but have some control over the price in final product markets, if market conditions permit, as detailed in the following sections. In this case, companies set prices higher than the (marginal) cost of producing the products so they can earn a profit. We assume that a sufficient number of firms are implementing circular strategies, thus having a non-negligible impact at the macro level. Lastly, a key tenet of our framework is that the supply of products and services is increasing in price.⁸

On the demand side, we assume that consumers earn money only through wages. This means their available budget is fixed —unless firms increase wages or prices declines. The aggregate quantity demanded decreases as the price increases.⁹ Societal preferences are slowly changing. That is to say, we do not analyze situations in which society-wide transformational effects occur. Specifically, we exclude cases where consumers suddenly fully embrace sufficiency or drastically reduce consumption for environmental and sustainability reasons. A significant proportion of consumers are willing to pay more for circular goods. This means that these products can easily replace traditional ones in meeting their

⁶This means that we do not consider the implementation of circular strategies that replace existing ones. This would imply opportunity costs in terms of resource use in choosing one or another circular strategy (Figge and Thorpe, 2019), but this is relevant to the study of maximum resource use mitigation. In this framework, we simply study the variation of resource use at the macro level, i.e., whether resource use declines or not.

⁷According to Reinhardt et al. (2008), firms treat socially responsible actions like any other business activity, pursuing only those initiatives that align with their financial objectives rather than engaging in altruistic profit sacrifices.

⁸A supply increasing in price characterizes markets defined as natural monopolies. This scenario has yet to be thoroughly examined in the rebound effect literature.

⁹Note that regarding intermediate demand, the assumption of decreasing demand in price is implied by the profit-maximizing assumption: Firms minimize costs and thus look for the cheapest inputs for a given quality.

Table 1: Micro-circular strategies and counterparts

counterpart	description	examples
FINANCIAL COUNTERPART	Impact on production costs, company revenues, prices and downstream markets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower production costs through material efficiency, reducing prices and stimulating downstream demand. • Higher selling prices from costlier repairable products, impacting competing products and other markets through effects on consumer budgets and preferences (substitution effect).
MATERIAL COUNTERPART	Aggregate material impact of the circular strategies on markets, until material markets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced material demand through lightweight products, sharing systems, in-house reuse. • Additional supply of materials (in recycled form or embodied in products) through recycling, reuse, and remanufacturing, that would have otherwise been discarded as waste. • Additional demand for recycled materials and products substituting to demand for virgin materials.
RESOURCE COUNTERPART	Indirect impact of the circular strategies on the resource mix (materials and energy) to implement the circular strategy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional energy demand for recycling and digital sharing systems. • Additional material demand for creating stocks of spared parts, new machinery. • Substitution with traditional production methods.

needs or preferences.¹⁰

3 From Micro-Circularity to Macro-Mitigation

This section identifies the economic mechanisms arising from firms' implementation of circular strategies. In this context, firm-level circular practices influence three key dynamics that have repercussions beyond company boundaries. First, implementing circular strategies affects production costs, prices, and demand in downstream markets and firms' investment decisions. We label this channel "financial counterpart". Second, the implementation of circular strategies affects the aggregate demand and supply of materials and the materials embedded in intermediate and final goods. We call this channel "material counterpart". Third, implementing circular strategies ultimately affects the quantity of inputs and the mix of materials and energy required to produce circular products and services. We label this channel "resource counterpart".

Table 1 summarizes the concepts related to the three counterparts and provides some illustrative examples. In the rest of this Section, we discuss each of these channels in detail.

¹⁰This assumption should be viewed cautiously, as Boyer et al. (2021) shows only a small segment actively prioritizes circular products over price considerations. However, our qualitative framework only requires that these consumer segments exist to enable the increased price channel mechanism, not that they constitute a majority.

3.1 Financial counterpart: pass-through on output prices, downstream market adjustments, and allocation of gains

The financial counterpart encompasses all those effects that derive from the impact of circular practices on the firm's production costs and, consequently, the prices it charges and the profit it makes. Observing aggregate effects requires analyzing each firm's strategic pricing response within its market. We then need to aggregate these individual outcomes to determine the overall impact. Given that circular practices may both decrease and increase the firm's production costs, we analyze the two opposite cases separately. For each case, we discuss the firm's pricing behavior and its decisions regarding the use of any additional profit. Lastly, we analyze what we call *substitution effects*.

3.1.1 Lower production costs

If circular strategies imply lower production costs, the revenue/cost ratio for the firm increases. Some firms may retain these cost savings entirely as higher profit margins or use them to expand activities through higher wages or reinvestment, while others may pass part or all of the savings onto consumers, resulting in lower output prices.

The extent to which a firm can translate cost savings into higher margins or lower prices depends on its market power, i.e., its ability to set a price higher than the unit cost of production. Economic theory predicts that the more competitive a market, the lower the firm's market power. In a perfectly competitive market, the price of output equals the marginal cost. In such a market, any cost savings experienced by the firm will be fully passed on to consumers through reduced prices (e.g., [Loy et al. \(2016\)](#), [Genakos and Pagliero \(2022\)](#)). Conversely, the firm can keep a higher margin if it has market power. It can also gain market power as a result of the perceived higher quality of the new circular product/service.

We first discuss the case of markets with a relatively high degree of competition, i.e., where cost savings almost entirely translate into lower output price. According to standard economic theory, if the price of the firm's good/service decreases, the quantity of the specific good demanded by consumers increases, *ceteris paribus* ([Sorrell and Dimitropoulos, 2008](#); [Metic and Pigosso, 2022](#)). This effect can partially or completely offset any material savings achieved through the adoption of a circular strategy. This mechanism can be assimilated to a *direct rebound effect* as defined in relation to energy use by [Greening et al. \(2000\)](#).¹¹ The magnitude of this "direct" rebound will depend on how elastic the demand for the circular good is, namely how strongly consumers react to price changes (Feature B_1 in Figure 2). If the demand is very elastic, consumers will significantly in-

¹¹Our approach to the rebound concept differs from the existing literature in that we do not assume circular strategies automatically deliver environmental benefits. Instead, these benefits must be evaluated across all three counterparts. Nevertheless, the mechanisms are similar.

crease the quantity consumed as a result of the price decrease. In this extreme case, total resource consumption may increase as a result of the circular strategy. The *direct* rebound effect will be nil only if consumers do not react to changes in price because their demand is fully inelastic beyond a certain quantity, i.e., "fully saturated".¹²

Furthermore, a lower production cost for a given product not only impacts its price and demand but also results in a higher available budget for consumers. As a result, consumers will likely choose to purchase other (non-circular) products and services through *re-spending*, giving rise to an *indirect rebound* (Greening et al., 2000; Sorrell, 2009; Santarius, 2012; Metic and Pigosso, 2022; Heun et al., 2025).¹³ The overall resource mitigation of a given firm-level circular strategy will therefore depend on (i) the saturation of these other markets (Feature B_1), following a dynamics similar to the one described for the direct rebound effect, and (ii) the resource-intensity of the other products (see Appendix B). Additionally, the presence of a circular product in the market can give rise to substitution effects. These effects, which are connected to consumers' preferences, will be discussed in detail in Section 3.1.3.

If firms operate in less competitive markets, as a result of lower production costs, output prices decrease only partially and firms can retain part of the gains by increasing their margins (Feature A_1).¹⁴ The impact of higher margins on resource mitigation depends on the resource intensity of the firm's rent allocation. On the one hand, the firm can distribute additional rent to workers through wage increases. In this case, the wage earners (consumers) may allocate their budget to additional consumption, thereby generating a rebound. The size of this material rebound depends on the resource intensity of these additional products and services (Feature B_2). On the other hand, the firm can decide to distribute the rent to its shareholders or increase investment. A rebound effect will emerge if the newly financed activities are resource-intensive (Santarius, 2012; Metic and Pigosso, 2022). Importantly, an "extraction" rebound can occur if investments are made in resource exploitation and extraction. This is likely when these activities are not constrained (Feature C). For this reason, Life Cycle Assessments should always account for how earnings from sales are used (Thiesen et al., 2008).

Incidentally, when firms benefit from high market power, they can also increase the price of the circular product (Chenavaz et al., 2021), leading to even higher margins (Feature A_2). Indeed, products acquire new circular characteristics that modify consumer payment willingness, potentially allowing for higher pricing (e.g., Boyer et al., 2021; Chenavaz

¹²Also note that increased sales mean more profit for the firm, thus potentially giving rise to dynamics similar to those which characterize less competitive markets, described below.

¹³This is the case if the demand of other goods and services is not saturated, an assumption which is in line with the observed trends of increased consumption worldwide.

¹⁴Indeed, the literature shows that in more concentrated markets, selling prices tend to be more rigid when it comes to lowering them following a reduction in production costs (Loy et al., 2016).

et al., 2021).¹⁵ Price increases can also occur when firms deliberately limit production, as with limited editions, creating a scarcity-driven price effect. We discuss the dynamics of increased prices in more detail in the following Section 3.1.2.

3.1.2 Higher production costs

While circular practices are typically associated with costless efficiency gains in the literature (Böhringer and Rivers, 2021), such strategies may in fact result in higher production costs. This is the case if firms need to acquire knowledge, skills, or machinery, develop new processes, search for new partners in the value chain, or reorganize logistics. The right-hand side of Figure 2 illustrates the possible economic mechanisms following such an increase in production costs, starting from the output price of the firm and its profit margins.

If production costs increase, firms must then be able to raise prices to maintain (or to increase) their profit margin. As discussed above, if a sufficiently high share of consumers has a higher marginal willingness to pay for circular products than for traditional products, sales remain sufficiently large despite the higher prices charged for the circular product.

In line with what is described in Section 3.1.1, in a market with a relatively high degree of competition, the output price would increase to the level equal to the marginal cost, as firms have no market power to increase it further and raise their margins. Conversely, if firms have market power (Feature A_3), they can capitalize on consumers' eco-sensitivity by imposing a cost pass-through that exceeds 100% and consequently increase their margin. In all these situations, the possibility of a *direct* or *indirect* rebound from the consumer's side is limited (Chenavaz et al., 2021). Indeed, assuming an unchanged budget and ignoring consumers' decisions to change the relative consumption of goods in their basket (the so-called substitution effect, described in Section 3.1.3), consumers' purchasing power becomes comparatively lower.¹⁶ This will ultimately put downward pressure on the consumption of any product, whether more or less resource-intensive and whether circular or not.

However, higher resource use could still materialize as an outcome if firms' increased profits are distributed via wages or to shareholders, likely resulting in higher consumption or investment. Note that this event is less likely to occur if production costs increase rather than decrease (see Section 3.1.1). Indeed, higher resource use from allocating additional rents to resource-intensive activities can, in theory, be partially offset. This can occur because higher final product prices may reduce overall demand.

¹⁵Note that a high marginal willingness to pay implies that consumers perceive the circular good as of the same or higher quality with respect to the non-circular good. A perception of too low quality is incompatible with setting a high margin.

¹⁶The profit-maximization hypothesis implies that the consumption adjustment does not negatively impact the firm's profit. Hence, decreased sales mostly affect other goods and services by assumption.

In addition to the dynamics of higher or lower production costs, circular practices can also represent new business opportunities, leading to a situation where production costs cannot be compared at the firm level. This is the case, for instance, when a car-selling company develops a new branch or a subsidiary company providing a car-sharing service. In this case, firms introduce a new product that competes with existing products, as detailed in the substitution effect below (Section 3.1.3). Yet, the profits generated from the new business follow the same pathways we just described. They can be allocated to salaries, stakeholder returns, and/or investments.

3.1.3 Substitution effect

The effects described in Sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 can be further compounded by "substitution effects" in the downstream market. When a circular version of a product or service is distinguishable from its non-circular alternative, it can alter consumer preferences—that is, the relative weight given to the consumption of the different goods in consumer utility. In parallel, the introduction of the circular good reshapes the competitive landscape by influencing the relative prices of available alternatives. For example, when consumers are presented with new grocery shopping options, such as a ‘zero packaging’ store versus a traditional supermarket, they will reassess their previous consumption choices. This reassessment is based on updated preferences regarding packaging waste generation and the relative prices of grocery items.

The substitution effect differs from the re-spending effect discussed in Section 3.1.1. The substitution effect occurs when preferences change (while the budget remains constant), whereas the re-spending occurs when the budget changes (abstracting from updated preferences).¹⁷

As pictured in Figure 2, the substitution effect triggered by the presence of a new circular product can reduce, amplify, or even reverse any *direct* and *indirect* rebound effects. The final effect depends on whether the circular product replaces a less or a more resource-intensive product. For instance, if consumers redirect their consumption towards resource-sober products, any direct rebound effect arising as a result of lower prices of circular products can be dampened or canceled (Demonstration in Appendix C). However, the opposite situation is also possible. Circular products can replace less resource-intensive ones, strengthening the rebound. For example, if engaging in car sharing substitutes walking or cycling, resource consumption increases as a result of a substitution effect (Metic and Pigosso, 2022).

Similar substitution dynamics also characterize firms’ profit (re-)allocation since the development of circular strategies can attract firms’ investments.

¹⁷This can be equivalent to a fixed basket composition, unless in the case of saturated demands, which can constrain the basket composition

In summary, preventing resource increases requires both demand saturation (lock B) and constrained extraction (lock C), along with substitution effects that favor low-resource-intensive consumption. Section 4 presents policy instruments to support these conditions.

3.2 Material counterpart: Impact on supply and demand of materials

The material counterpart encompasses all effects resulting from the fact that circular strategies directly influence the aggregate demand and supply of materials. This applies to both raw inputs and materials embodied in products and components, extending all the way to upstream markets.¹⁸ Hence, this Section focuses on the aggregate effect of the adjustment of intermediate product prices and quantities resulting from the simultaneous implementation of circular strategies by many small firms. By assumption, each firm alone would not affect upstream markets, but their combined actions can produce measurable impacts.¹⁹ We detail three specific dynamics, which can compound at the aggregate level. Circular practices may result in: i) decreased material demand; ii) increased material supply; iii) increased secondary material demand. Finally, we describe the substitution effect, which refers to the extent to which circular products can replace non-circular ones.

3.2.1 Decreased material demand

First, we discuss the dynamics triggered by companies positioned in the value chain as providers of circular services or products, and as purchasers of materials or intermediate components. These companies can adopt circular strategies, such as implementing material-efficient design, in-house reuse, and sharing, which may reduce their material requirements. As illustrated in Figure 3, at the aggregated level, this results in a downward shift (from D to D_1) of the intermediate product demand curve across all price levels.²⁰ According to standard economic theory, if supply is fixed (Feature C), this reduces the price of the good (from p to p'). This price adjustment partially offset the potential reduction in quantity demanded ($Q - Q'$), as lower prices encourage increased consumption.²¹ If demand is not saturated (Feature B), in equilibrium the quantity of products - and,

¹⁸Contrary to the effect detailed in the *financial counterpart*, which is related to firms' downstream markets and individual firm pricing strategies.

¹⁹The material counterpart can thus refer to the *economy-wide rebound effect* in the terminology of Greening et al. (2000).

²⁰We assume that circular strategies leading to reduced material needs do not change price elasticity, i.e., do not affect the demand curve slope.

²¹The effect differs from the financial counterpart in that it represents an aggregate adjustment in the upstream market, whereas the financial counterpart reflects an adjustment in the firms' downstream demand.

Figure 3: Market adjustment following decreased material demand

hence, material - is higher (Q'') than it would have been if prices had remained constant (Q'). This standard economic adjustment characterizes the rebound effect pertaining to decreased material demand.

The extent of this rebound will depend on the magnitude of the price drop, which is influenced by the elasticity of both supply and demand (as demonstrated by [Borenstein, 2015](#) and [Böhringer and Rivers, 2021](#) for energy efficiency improvements).

Rebound effects can be limited by preventing price adjustments that would otherwise stimulate additional demand. For instance, constraining the supply of materials (supply curve S_C), can maintain the original price level p , thereby avoiding the demand-side rebound that would result from lower prices. Alternatively, if demand saturates at the lower quantity level Q' (demand curve D_B), firms do not respond to price drops. These conditions, their feasibility, and the associated policy measures, are further discussed in [Section 4](#).

3.2.2 Increased material supply

Second, we discuss the dynamic triggered by companies that are positioned in the value chain as suppliers of secondary materials and products. In this case, companies engage in circular strategies by supplying recycled materials or reused intermediate and final products. If secondary products that would otherwise be discarded are injected or reintroduced into the market, the total supply of materials increases relative to a scenario

without circularity (Dace et al., 2014; Zink and Geyer, 2017). This adjustment is represented in Figure 4, through a downward shift in the supply curve (from S to S_1).²² According to standard economic theory, this downward shift in supply reduces the price of that product (from p to p'). As before, if demand is not saturated (Feature B) at the lower level Q , overall resource use increases (from Q to Q').

We acknowledge that this dynamic can be compounded by a possible substitution effect between secondary and primary products, detailed in Section 3.2.4. For the time being, we simply claim that the additional supply from secondary inputs expands overall material availability (Zink and Geyer, 2017).

Figure 4: Increased resource use from increased supply (for a given material)

Demand saturation (lock B) and constrained extraction (lock C) are again essential conditions to avoid material increase. Indeed, restricting extraction possibilities (i.e., negatively impacting supply) could constrain price declines on the material market and, thus, the increase in resource use. Moreover, as we discuss in Section 3.2.4, the substitution effect can also be leveraged to prevent an increase in total material use (Zink and Geyer, 2017).

²²If primary and secondary goods compete within the same market, the supply curve in Figure 4 (Panel II) can be interpreted as total material supply, comprising both primary and secondary sources. Conversely, if these goods compete in separate markets, for instance, due to substantial quality differences, the observed increase in supply reflects only the secondary goods component.

3.2.3 Increased secondary material demand

Third, we discuss dynamics arising when companies position themselves as buyers of secondary products in the value chain, and decide to incorporate recycled materials into their products or use secondary intermediate goods. Examples include refurbished machinery as inputs in the firm's production processes. This type of circular practice results in a higher demand for circular goods.

This mechanism, which pertains specifically to secondary materials and products, is the inverse of what was described in the "Decreased Material Demand" (Section 3.2.1). In Figure 3, it is represented as an upward shift in the demand curve for circular intermediate products (from D_1 to D). This increased demand raises the prices of secondary products, limiting the overall increase in their consumption while incentivizing the expansion of collection and processing of waste materials.

3.2.4 Substitution effect

In this Section, we discuss how substitution dynamics between primary and secondary products compound those discussed in Section 3.2.2 and 3.2.3. Indeed, a crucial assumption of our analysis is that circular products have a (high-to-low) potential to replace their non-circular alternative (see Section 2), given their technical characteristics. The actual extent of substitution will depend on demand considerations, i.e., whether consumers and firms purchase the circular products in place of the non-circular alternatives.

In this context, two opposite scenarios need to be discussed: incomplete substitution and over-complete substitution. The case of down-cycling is arguably a case of incomplete substitution (Afif et al., 2024); on the other hand, sharing systems can represent a case of over-substitution (e.g., when the sharing of a single item effectively replaces the purchase of multiple items).

As illustrated in Figure 4, if the supply of secondary material increases, the supply curve shifts from S to S_1 and resource use increases from Q to Q' . If the demand for secondary material simultaneously increases, the demand for primary inputs may decrease, depending on the degree of substitutability.

In the case of incomplete substitution (Figure 5, Panel a), the increased demand for secondary inputs does not fully offset the reduction in demand for primary inputs. Total demand rises from D_{V+R} to D_{V+R}^1 . Combining both supply and demand shifts, resource use will increase up to Q'' . This is greater than Q' , namely the equilibrium that only results from a shift in supply. Hence, incomplete substitution gives rise to dynamics that compound the upward pressure on resource use.

In the case of "over-complete substitution" (Panel b), the use of one circular input makes it possible to replace more than one virgin/non-circular input. Total demand de-

a) incomplete substitution

Figure 5: Illustration of substitution scenarios: incomplete substitution (left) and over-complete substitution (right)

creases (from D_{V+R} to D_{V+R}^1). Combining both supply and demand shifts, resource use will decrease to Q'' , which is smaller than Q' . The possibility of "over-complete substitution" between circular and non-circular inputs can therefore counteract the effect of a concomitant increase in supply.

Therefore, one potential strategy to favor resource mitigation is to restrict the supply by constraining extraction and fostering strong potential for substitution. This strategy is more likely to succeed if circular materials can serve as true substitutes for primary alternatives (Zink and Geyer, 2017).

3.3 Resource counterpart

The resource counterpart relates to the material and energy inputs needed to implement circular practices at the firm level. It also accounts for cascading effects on materials and energy across sectors, driven by value chain interdependency and the adaptive responses of downstream actors.

At the firm level, implementing a circular strategy likely requires additional energy and material, including those embedded in new capital inputs. These aspects have not yet been accounted for in our analysis of the material counterpart. Producing thinner packaging may require new machinery; sharing systems often rely on digital infrastructure; and recycling or reusing materials typically involves energy use and capital investment, including those for transportation. A rich literature highlights the importance of accounting

for the energy requirements of circular strategies, especially for energy-intensive processes such as recycling (Gai et al., 2021; Di Domenico et al., 2023; Potting et al., 2017), or related to the lifetime extension of energy-intensive products (Hummen and Desing, 2021; Iraldo et al., 2017).

Spillovers along the value chain can occur if, for example, consumers spend more resources to access a circular good, e.g., drive to a more distant supermarket that offers zero-waste choices.²³ When discussing the implications related to the resource counterpart, two factors especially matter. First, the degree of substitutability or complementarity between the materials and the energy used for the service provided by the circular good across the value chain. Second, how closely the circular good matches the quality of its conventional alternative (e.g., see Wei, 2010). For example, circular strategies like "refuse", which reduce plastic packaging for final consumers, might reduce the quantity of plastic in stores, but still result in higher overall resource use. This can happen if plastic and the other resources employed, such as energy and resources needed for logistics and transportation, are substitutes for one another across the value chain. This substitution effect is a technical one and does not relate to specific consumer preferences.

While fostering the use of circular goods over non-circular goods (Sections 3.1 and 3.2), it is important to account for the resource counterpart, thus verifying whether circular goods have a lower per unit resource impact compared to all the resources needed for non-circular goods (Zink and Geyer, 2017). Addressing this issue requires closing a fundamental knowledge gap on the extent to which different materials and energy sources act as substitutes or complements. Both the applied economics and engineering literature show that these relationships are not straightforward and vary across contexts (Long and Schipper, 1978).²⁴ Importantly, the literature suggests a certain degree of proportionality between materials and energy while also indicating that some materials can be substituted with energy. Such complex effects can be better understood through life cycle assessments at the product level (Iraldo et al., 2017) supplemented by market analyses to identify adjustments in value chains.²⁵

This knowledge is fundamental to designing policy interventions that avoid undermining the circular strategies.²⁶ For instance, the overall effect of restricting the supply of

²³In the example of the zero-waste supermarket, we can see the problem as a "quality" issue. The circular service is perceived as superior in terms of utility, as consumers are willing to spend additional resources to access it. However, the service entails a "technical" drawback in terms of accessibility. Avoiding loss of quality services, which includes accessibility, could prevent this type of rebound. However, note that as consumers' budget is fixed, this type of increased consumption (e.g., driving) would substitute for other expenses and purchases, impacting the financial counterpart.

²⁴e.g., see (Aditya et al., 2017) for an example of substitutability between insulation materials and energy consumption

²⁵Indeed, any increase or decrease in demand for resource inputs will prompt price adjustments, which will in turn encourage or constrain demand in other markets, similar to the mechanisms described in the material counterpart.

²⁶Note that these measures can be costly in terms of data collection and analyses, and modelers can

a given material varies depending on its degree of substitutability with other materials and with energy. If the material is a complement to other materials/energy, restricting only its supply can ensure an overall reduction in resource use. If the material is a substitute for other materials/energy, this is not the case. Thus, achieving an overall reduction in resource use would require either restricting all relevant resources or allowing limited substitutability to the extent that it still delivers net resource mitigation. Moreover, some degree of substitutability may be necessary for implementing the circular strategy itself. For example, if reducing plastic packaging for consumers entails greater material use in logistics (e.g., wooden pallets or larger containers) or increased energy demand in transportation, overly stringent extraction limits on all resources could hinder the implementation of the circular strategy.

Resource accounting and consistency between the counterparts

To assess the impact of circular strategies on resource use, we need to consider the effects of the three counterparts jointly. Circular strategies might reduce resource use in one counterpart, but this could be counterbalanced by increased resource use in another. For instance, "reduced material demand" in the material counterpart can be partly or totally canceled by a direct rebound in the financial counterpart. In addition, substitution effects, like replacing non-circular products with circular ones, must be carefully accounted for to avoid double-counting. Finally, it is crucial to ensure that the three counterparts—financial, material, and resource—are consistent with one another. For example, assumptions made in one counterpart, like lower product quality or limited substitutability, should also inform the other counterparts.

3.4 From resource mitigation to a macro circular economy

Beyond resource use, it is important to analyze extraction and disposal flows, which are closely linked to the overall level of resource use and have significant implications for climate change. In fact, resource extraction and processing, including biomass, fossil fuels, metals, and non-metallic minerals, contribute to over 90% of global biodiversity loss and water stress, and around 50% of global greenhouse gas emissions (not accounting for land use changes) (UNEP, 2019). Yet, global resource extraction has surged from 27 billion tons in 1970 to 92 billion tons in 2017. Along similar lines, waste disposal impacts on land use, biodiversity, and climate change (UNEP, 2019).

As lower resource use is compatible with both higher extraction levels and higher waste disposal, we now analyze the conditions under which resource mitigation leads to both reduced extraction of virgin materials and lower disposal.

account for them in the financial counterpart under production costs.

3.4.1 From resource mitigation to reduced extraction

Resource mitigation can be defined as $\Delta V + \Delta Z < 0$, where V denotes the use of virgin resources and Z represents the use of secondary materials. In this Section, we assume that $\Delta V + \Delta Z < 0$, namely that resource mitigation has been achieved, and we examine the conditions under which a reduction in overall resource extraction can also be achieved.

Quite obviously, resource mitigation leads to lower extraction if $\Delta V < 0$, meaning that the reduction in resource use is achieved through a decrease in virgin resource consumption and not solely through a reduction in the use of secondary materials. Recall that limiting extraction has also been identified as a crucial condition for mitigating rebound effects in resource use. Reduced extraction is already a key favorable condition for achieving resource use mitigation. Hence, there is a two-way connection between resource mitigation and resource extraction, as illustrated by the double arrow in Figure 1. Indeed, a lower level of resource extraction is often used as a key indicator of success in implementing the circular economy (Ottelin et al., 2020; Mostert et al., 2021).²⁷

3.4.2 From resource mitigation to reduced disposal

As before, in this Section we assume that resource mitigation has been achieved ($\Delta V + \Delta Z < 0$) and explore the conditions under which resource mitigation leads to reduced disposal. Unlike reduced extraction, reduced disposal also needs to be examined at the micro level, as circular strategies can both positively and negatively affect the lifespan of products, and thus the flow of materials intended for disposal. Therefore, we analyse conditions at both the micro and macro levels.

Circular strategies could, in some instances, shorten product lifespan if they push firms and consumers to dispose of the products before the end of their natural lifetime. This could occur, for example, if second-hand markets create resale opportunities, but buyers do not retain items for long (e.g., due to a lower perceived value of the goods) compared with the scenario of no reselling opportunities. This implies that, at the micro level, a sufficient condition for circular strategies to reduce disposal is that they do not hasten the product's end-of-life. The direct effect of circular strategies on reduced disposal is illustrated by the upper arrow in Figure 1.²⁸

To set the condition at the macro-level, let R represent total resource use in the economy, D disposal, S the quantity issued from the economy's material stock, and Z the quantity of materials that is recycled. Hence, $D = R + S - Z$, and its evolution

²⁷Alongside the material footprint concept, defined as the "total amount of raw materials extracted to meet final consumption demands" by the United Nations (2023).

²⁸Recall that the focus of our analysis is on circular strategies, substituting "no circular strategy". Conversely, we do not consider cases in which firms shift from one circular strategy (e.g., recycling) to another (e.g., repair), in which case we would need different conditions for reduced disposal.

is given by $\Delta D = \Delta R + \Delta S - \Delta Z$. Now, assuming resource mitigation ($\Delta R < 0$), we can observe a reduction in macro-level disposal ($\Delta D < 0$) if recycled quantities are stable or increase ($\Delta Z \geq 0$) or if they decrease less than resource use and destocking ($|\Delta R| + |\Delta S| > |\Delta Z|$).²⁹

On the contrary, if the recycling rate decreases, macro-level disposal could increase despite thinner material flows. Hence, at the macro level, a sufficient condition for circular strategies to reduce disposal is that the recycling rate is maintained so that a reduction in the use of materials leads to a decrease in macro-level disposal, under constant de-stocking.

4 Conditions For A Macro Circular Economy And Possible Policy Levers

As Section 3 shows, market features —the degree of competition in the market, the degree of demand saturation, and whether extraction is constrained— and substitution dynamics are essential in determining if firm-level circular strategies reduce economy-wide resources. This is true for each counterpart —financial, material, and resource. Moreover, high recycling rates and extended product lifespans are necessary to ensure that resource mitigation efforts result in reduced disposal. These conditions ultimately refer to the circular strategies themselves and likewise highlight the importance of fostering them in their full diversity. In light of this, we discuss the policy levers related to each of these factors: Section 4.1 focuses on policies connected to market features, Section 4.2 discusses instruments to leverage substitution effects, and Section 4.3 discusses policy measures related to recycling and product lifespans.

4.1 Navigating market features

4.1.1 Condition A: Redirecting the rents

As Section 3.1 demonstrates, market power plays a key role in shaping the pathway through which circular strategies may or may not lead to resource mitigation. However, a given degree of market competition—whether high or low—cannot indicate whether circular strategies will result in lower resource consumption: both excessive firm margins (resulting from monopolistic markets) and low prices (resulting from competitive markets) can lead to increased resource use. This implies that lower macro-level resource use cannot be achieved by simply regulating the degree of competition in a given market, for example, through antitrust regulation.³⁰

²⁹See resource flows in Haas et al. (2020)

³⁰Nevertheless, while our framework does not directly discuss the distribution of rents, we note that if this is such that inequality increases, the literature provides some evidence that overall environmental

Figure 6: Conditions for circular strategies to lead to resource mitigation

Notes: The green boxes in the Figure indicate the conditions that help counteract the rebound effects. Conditions presented to the left are connected to the market features. Conditions to the right leverage the substitution effects.

What ultimately matters is whether the additional rents captured by consumers and firms are allocated to resource-sober or resource-saving activities. Understanding whether the rents arising from circular practices are concentrated or broadly distributed — and which actors benefit from them — is essential for designing effective policy interventions. A targeted use of fiscal instruments or policies that are cognizant of, and exploit, substitution effects can help steer these economic rents toward resource-saving activities, thereby reinforcing the environmental benefits of circularity. We further discuss this point in 4.2.1, where we present policy incentives for resource-sober investments or demand-side interventions.

4.1.2 Condition B: Demand saturation

Saturation in either intermediate or final demand (the activation of lock B) *de facto* results in a congestion effect. Importantly, saturation in final (i.e., consumer) demand is crucial in our framework as it implies a given level of saturation also in intermediate demand. Conversely, the opposite is not true. Final (consumer) demand saturation can arise from either temporal or physical constraints (e.g., limited storage; Zink and Geyer, 2017), or quality may be negatively affected (Boyce, 1994; Magnani, 2000; Berthe and Elie, 2015). Since companies are more likely than consumers to concentrate rents among a small number of actors—thereby contributing to inequality—it may be more important to focus on rents captured by firms. We leave this topic for future research.

from environmental beliefs and preferences (Dace et al., 2014), resulting in a congestion effect.³¹

While (quasi-)saturation patterns are common at the product or sectoral levels, natural saturation of aggregate final demand appears highly unlikely in reality. Over time, market penetration of representative products (e.g., cars) tends to follow a S-shaped curve (Aoki and Yoshikawa, 2002). Diffusion starts slowly, grows rapidly once a critical mass is reached, and then levels off until it reaches saturation. Yet, saturation of aggregate final demand appears highly unlikely in reality, particularly in light of the pressing need from the Global South to achieve decent standards of living (IPCC, 2022; Kikstra et al., 2025).

Policies thus represent a instrument to promote or accelerate saturation in specific products or sectors. Available policy levers include nudging consumers toward sufficiency-oriented lifestyles and encouraging the durability of bulky goods, thereby creating a congestion effect. In the building sector, for example, strategies of urban planning such as compact city development, rationalization of living spaces, and innovative architectural design, can successfully restrict demand for floor space per capita and for long-distance travel (Creutzig et al., 2022; Mastrucci et al., 2023).³² Note that if supply is limited (e.g., in housing), competition to access the good drives prices up. Consumption will thus be limited by physical and budgetary constraints. Yet, this situation can create significant rent effects, the allocation of which impacts resource mitigation, as already discussed above.

Importantly, the natural saturation of product- or sector-level demand may still occur at levels of resource use that exceed sustainable limits, thus failing to ensure resource mitigation and respect planetary boundaries. In addition, saturation in one product or activity can be offset by increased consumption of other (more resource-intensive) goods. Similarly, efforts towards sufficiency by one group of consumers may trigger rebound effects through higher consumption by others (Figge et al., 2014).³³ In such cases, a specific policy lever—such as quotas—can force the saturation *level* of certain demand for certain consumer groups. Xin et al. (2012) suggests quotas for energy consumption of four and five-star luxury hotel buildings in Hainan, China. However, quotas on one consumption item are not exempt from the risk of rebound, e.g., by encouraging energy efficiency development and shifting consumption expenditure to other resource-intensive

³¹Demand saturation differs from simple preferences affecting the weight of utility and marginal willingness to pay. In case of saturation, even for very low prices, a certain consumption threshold cannot be exceeded; while in "shifting preferences" (condition 4.2.2), the demand never becomes price-inelastic. As this is a very unlikely situation, we also explore quasi-saturation as an approximation below.

³²Note that the effective potential of these solutions is still to be fully understood since their modeling is most often than not quite simplistic. In most of the modeling literature reviewed in our analysis, floorspace levels adjust exogenously to compact urban form and co-housing without explicitly accounting for the underlying socio-economic drivers (Mastrucci et al., 2023).

³³If only a minority of consumers shift toward sufficiency, prices may drop, encouraging higher consumption among others. In this case, only the demand curve for "sufficient" consumers becomes inelastic, while overall demand remains responsive (Figge et al., 2014).

items.

To effectively mitigate the risks of increased resource use, demand saturation policies should primarily target resource-intensive products and the largest resource holders, encompass as many products and consumers as possible, and define a level of saturation that remains compatible with planetary boundaries. This is a complex exercise as saturation objectives require a trade-off with other sustainable development goals and should not come at the expenses of achieving a decent standard of living for all (IPCC, 2022).³⁴ Furthermore, the political acceptability of demand saturation policies is not obvious by either firms or consumers.

4.1.3 Condition C: Limiting the extraction of virgin resources through quantities or costs

Limiting resource extraction is a goal on its own for achieving a macro circular economy (Section 3.4.1) and represents a potential lock to prevent increased resource use in the different counterparts (Sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3). There are at least two policy approaches to reducing the quantity of resources extracted.

First, resource extraction can be directly limited through regulation, such as biodiversity conservation plans, limits and quotas on extraction activities, or more democratic decision systems (Bareille et al., 2023) and well-defined governance rules (Ostrom, 1990). For instance, the Natura 2000 network, established under EU Directives³⁵ to protect biodiversity, spans 17.9% of the EU’s terrestrial area (Tsiafouli et al., 2013). In Brazil, deforestation of Amazonian lands by land stewards is limited to 20% of the controlled land (Código Florestal; Börner et al., 2014). In the fishing industry, quotas are common (e.g., see Newell et al., 2005).

Second, since higher extraction costs can reduce extraction rates (Faber and Proops, 1993), environmental standards or taxation can be used to impose additional compliance costs on firms (Pizer and Kopp, 2005). These higher costs translate into increased downstream resource prices, which in turn reduce demand. For example, the obligation to reclaim land after mining activities can add significant expenses to mining operations (Yu et al., 2020). In Europe, Directive 2006/21/EC requires the management of waste from extractive industries, mentioning soil rehabilitation following waste management activities. In parallel, if quantitative legal restrictions are enforced through effectively collected

³⁴To further explore the question of demand saturation, we refer readers to the work of Higgins (1972). Higgins (1972) theoretically demonstrates that, for a given income, there exist preferences that can allow for the saturation of demand for market commodities (e.g., energy or clothes) *relative* to non-market commodities (e.g., walks in nature or time spent with friends). Following our framework, we would add to this theoretical consideration that to achieve resource mitigation, these non-market activities must be resource-saving, or at least resource-sober.

³⁵established under two EU Directives: the Birds (79/409/EEC; 2009/147/EU) and the Habitats (92/43/EEC) Directive (Tsiafouli et al., 2013)

penalties, they increase production costs in a manner similar to taxes (Börner et al., 2014). Modeling exercises by UNEP (2019) show that rebound effects from increased resource efficiency can be mitigated through gradually increasing extraction taxes. Söderholm (2011) shows that taxes on aggregates (gravel, rock, stone, etc.) in Europe have contributed to reducing virgin resource use.

Restricting extraction in practice through any policy intervention is far from easy. Virgin resources are traded in a fragmented legislative world, and environmental policies intertwine with economic interests. In practice, biodiversity protection policies often permit certain extraction activities to maintain economic prosperity and oversight, and to prevent incentives for illegal operations. They sometimes fail to impose restrictions or raise extraction costs. According to Yu et al. (2020), for instance, when land reclamation is combined with economic development initiatives, the investment cost of reclamation can be recovered (Yu et al., 2020), thus offsetting increased costs. Tsiafouli et al. (2013) find that mining, extraction, and industrial activities were reported at 17.6 % of all sites in the national Natura 2000 networks. Although Europe’s Habitats Directive foresees that biodiversity maintenance may require human activities (Directive 92/43/EEC), industrial and mining activities are likely to be connected with environmental degradation (Tsiafouli et al., 2013). In Brazil, most of the observed deforestation is carried out illegally (Börner et al., 2014).

Ultimately, effectively regulating extraction requires the implementation of either strong economic incentives or the development of strong environmental preferences in favor of preserving ecosystems and extractive limits.

4.2 Leveraging substitution effects

Three conditions ensure that substitution effects support the achievement of resource mitigation. First, circular goods must be competitive in terms of price or quality with their non-circular alternatives. Second, preferences for low-resource consumption must be strong. Third, effective information on product and service resource intensity and substitution and complementarity relationships between inputs must be widely available.

4.2.1 Competitiveness of circular goods under horizontal competition

If circular goods and services are competitive in terms of price and/or quality, they easily substitute non-circular alternatives. As discussed in Section 3.1, price competitiveness may arise naturally when circular production involves fewer materials, leading to lower production costs. It can also result from scaling up circular production, which reduces unit costs regardless of the amount of material used through economies of scale.

As for policy levers, price competitiveness can be achieved through economic instru-

ments such as taxes imposed on non-circular goods combined with subsidies granted to circular goods (Palmer and Walls, 1997). Direct regulation favoring circular goods can also be implemented. An example is the use of recycled content norms, which, however, require ensuring that recycled content meets industry standards (i.e., that technical substitutability in production is high). In general, policymakers should prioritize subsidies and normative instruments for high-quality circular products with demonstrated high effectiveness at displacing conventional alternatives (high or "over-complete" substitution).

4.2.2 Shifting preferences toward low-resource consumption

Shifting preferences toward goods and services with lower resource requirements can reduce demand for resource-intensive items and prevent perverse outcomes in which circular products displace activities that are already low in resource intensity (e.g., car-sharing instead of walking).³⁶ Consumer and investor preferences are shaped by factors such as moral satisfaction (Kahneman and Knetsch, 1992; Chowdhury, 2017), social norms (Lin and Niu, 2018; Bonan et al., 2025), habits, risk management strategies, and reputation concerns (Reinhardt et al., 2008).

Policymakers can leverage these factors through policy levers such as environmental awareness actions and education on citizens (Rosa et al., 2018; Ardoin and Bowers, 2020) and firms (Amore et al., 2019). For instance, Rosa et al. (2018) find that greater contact with nature during childhood is positively associated with self-reported pro-environmental behaviors as an adult.³⁷ At the consumer level, eco-labeling can alter perceived value, making low-resource goods more attractive (Bjørner et al., 2004). In parallel, Joel et al. (2025) show that green bonds are associated with firms' improved environmental performance. It is necessary to ensure that financial criteria actually embed lower levels of resource consumption.

Importantly, to encourage preferences for low-resource consumption, consumers and investors need to be aware of the resource intensity of various activities, a topic explored

³⁶Graphically, this is represented by a decreased willingness to pay for resource-intensive activities, causing an inward shift of their demand curve, while the demand for low-resource consumption items shifts outward. Changing preferences can also alter how sensitive consumers are to price changes (elasticity). If consumers become less attached to resource-intensive consumption, demand can become more elastic for these items, meaning price plays a larger role in their purchasing decisions. Conversely, demand for low-resource consumption activities may become less elastic. This suggests that price decreases should be contained for resource-intensive activities to prevent reinforcing their consumption. Note that "Shifting preferences" differs from our condition B, "Demand Saturation," as it pertains to the utility weight assigned to a consumption item, influencing both the intercept and slope of the demand curve. In contrast, demand saturation refers to a specific case of inelastic demand, where the demand curve becomes vertical beyond a certain threshold (maximum quantity). Unlike saturation, shifting preferences alone cannot fully lock the rebound effect because, if demand is highly elastic, any (high) quantity can still be reached at a given price (Dace et al., 2014). However, there exists a corresponding price level that can achieve the saturation quantity (i.e., "cap or tax" debates; Karp and Traeger, 2024).

³⁷The authors surveyed 224 young adults in Brazil.

in the following subsection 4.2.3.

4.2.3 Information provision and technologies for low-resource choices

The availability of accessible and reliable data on product and service resource intensity is key to enabling resource-efficient choices and preventing unintended rebounds. To this end, researchers need to employ methods and tools that quantify the resource use of specific processes, such as life-cycle analysis (LCA).³⁸ Applied to individual circular products, LCA allows assessment of resource efficiency and identification of potential trade-offs between different resources within a given circular practice.³⁹ The analysis should be extended as far as possible to the effects of interdependence between sectors and, thus, to a more aggregated level than traditional life cycle analysis.

To achieve a continuous and widely shared monitoring, policymakers should establish regulatory frameworks, such as mandatory reporting based on standardized LCAs or other methodologies, which are particularly useful for high-impact products. These requirements can be integrated into Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes to help track and mitigate rebound effects. Economic incentives, such as innovation grants, can also support the development, diffusion, and adoption of novel information technologies. Additionally, public procurement policies can be designed to favor suppliers that use verified LCA methodologies, further encouraging transparency and accountability across supply chains.

4.3 Maintaining a high recycling rate while maximizing product lifetime under resource mitigation

Section 3.4.2 presented two sufficient conditions that guarantee that resource mitigation effectively leads to reduced disposal. First, circular strategies must be implemented for end-of-life products that would otherwise be sent to disposal or aim to a longer life by design. Second, maintaining a high recycling rate and/or minimizing de-stocking is essential relative to the amount of resources consumed.⁴⁰

Various policy levers can help achieve these two conditions. For instance, cultural and design practices such as design for emotional durability (Chapman, 2009) can help avoid

³⁸Adhering to the R-hierarchy, where the Rs in the higher part of the hierarchy, such as refuse, are assumed to be more resource efficient than the Rs lower in the hierarchy, such as reuse, is only a rule of thumb, as there are many exceptions (Potting et al., 2017).

³⁹LCA is by no means an easy task since it requires very detailed data. Furthermore, LCAs are easier to run after a project is completed. This makes it difficult to use LCA to influence design decisions (Desing et al., 2021). There are ongoing developments in ex-ante analyses, but they require specialist knowledge to address uncertainty and face challenges related to data availability and comparability (Desing et al., 2021).

⁴⁰Of course, minimizing de-stocking must be weighed against the resource counterpart, particularly for energy-intensive goods.

the shortening of products’ lifetime. In addition, minimum recycling performance requirements, such as nationally mandated recycling targets, supported by financing mechanisms like EPR, can be used to maintain a high recycling rate. Volume-based targets can also help redirect waste away from incineration and landfills, but may also incentivize low-quality recycling (Morseletto, 2020). Hence Morseletto (2020) recommends high-quality recycling policy levers such as design for recyclability. On the demand side, recycled content can ensure that the supply of recycled materials produced finds a demand.

Note that the implementation of recycling incentives might inadvertently generate economic motivations for premature end-of-life processing, particularly for products with high material value—hence the importance of our sufficient condition to prevent shortening a product’s life. A rigorous examination of potential trade-offs between circular strategies is needed to achieve the three dimensions of a macro circular economy.

5 Implications for Climate Mitigation

The framework developed and discussed in this paper links circular economy practices at the micro level with resource mitigation, extraction, and disposal at the macro level. This Section briefly analyzes how a *macro circular economy* can contribute to climate mitigation. The channels from circularity to climate mitigation can be direct and indirect.

The direct channel relates to emissions arising from resource use through combustion and other chemical processes (e.g., calcification). In analyzing GHG mitigation, it is important to consider heterogeneity in resource emission content, which we have not addressed up to this point. Indeed, resource mitigation can still lead to increased emissions if the use of carbon-intensive resources increases relative to carbon-efficient ones. Yet, carbon intensity depends on the way resources are used (e.g., incineration) and thus varies depending on the specific technology and production process. In our framework, we assume a stable technology and thus, implicitly, consider carbon intensity as constant and exogenous for each resource. However, implementing circular practices can also influence the carbon intensity of resources. Specifically, recycling—when not excessively energy-intensive—can supply materials with a lower carbon footprint than virgin production (e.g., Saevarsdottir et al., 2020 for aluminum). Therefore, a crucial condition for ensuring that circular strategies effectively support climate mitigation is to prioritize the reduction of carbon-intensive resources, including virgin production when relevant.

The indirect channel relates to the fact that ecosystem carbon services are affected by resource extraction (ecosystem depletion) and waste disposal (disruption of ecosystem functions due to pollutants and waste discharge). Landfill and extraction destroy the potential habitats for flora and fauna, limiting biodiversity and climate services (Boldy et al., 2021). Mining activities impact climate change. Harvesting subsurface resources

can substantially transform the land typography and alter the flow of water (Boldy et al., 2021; Hoesen et al., 2023). This can cause enduring adverse impacts on biodiversity and associated ecosystem services (*ibidem*). Mining forests leads to the release of greenhouse gases due to forest loss. Disposal activities generate greenhouse gas emissions: methane is produced when organic material decomposes anaerobically (45% to 60% CH₄, 40% to 60% CO₂, and 2% to 9% other gases, Aljaradin and Persson, 2012), for instance, as a result of land filling. According to Gichamo and Gökçekuş (2019), the contribution of solid waste to climate change is relatively low. However, landfills represent an opportunity cost in terms of land use and climate. This space could be allocated to maintaining an area of biodiversity that helps regulate the climate. Since ecosystems yield different types of services and their capacity for climate stabilization varies spatially, the geographical aspects of resource provenance and disposal locations are critical factors in determining the overall climate impact of circular practices. Accordingly, reducing resource extraction and waste disposal offers an important opportunity for climate mitigation, particularly when it helps prevent further land degradation and safeguard climate-critical ecosystems. As for recovered land, the climate benefits depend on how the land is subsequently used.

6 Conclusion

Our framework outlines three distinct channels—financial, material, and resource—that link firm-level circular practices to macro-level resource use. We identify the critical factors influencing the potential for lower or higher resource use, which need to be considered strategically. Importantly, this requires addressing demand saturation, constraining extractive possibilities, managing rents from circular strategies, and fostering preferences for resource-sober goods and services.

Most of our conditions for resource mitigation pose challenges regarding political acceptability and international governmental cooperation.⁴¹ This underscores the inherent difficulty in managing rebound effects systemically, helping explain why societies continue to fall short of their environmental objectives. Of course, some conditions could restrict all types of rebound—for instance, demand saturation above a certain level or restrictions on all resource extraction—but are unlikely to be fully applicable. Instead, our conditions can be deployed as a policy mix, enabling policymakers to assess implementation feasibility within their specific national or regional contexts.

Our analysis offers several useful insights to researchers in engineering and material modeling of circularity. First, it points to potential shortcomings in currently available modeling tools, which generally lack the ability to precisely model the financial counterpart (including market features). Second, it highlights the importance of transparency

⁴¹Figure 6 summarizes the applicable conditions and associated policy levers for each rebound channel.

in model assumptions—particularly regarding the relative substitutability of circular versus non-circular goods and the presence or absence of consumer preferences for circularity—and emphasizes the need to test the robustness of results through sensitivity analysis. Third, it calls for the development of circular narratives that can serve as storylines to explicitly account for aspects—such as market features—that cannot be meaningfully incorporated into models without adding excessive complexity.

Our findings also put forward three additional policy implications. First, taxation alone does not guarantee resource mitigation. We have identified taxes in the policy mix for resource mitigation, but the tax system will effectively achieve this objective only if it discourages resource-intensive expenditures while ensuring revenue recycling into resource-efficient or resource-saving activities. Without proper revenue recycling, taxation will fail to deliver meaningful decreases in resource consumption. For instance, investing in public transportation could be an efficient tax recycling activity.

Second, environmental preferences are not only a key condition to leverage substitution effects, but also fundamental to the broader success of any policy measure. To be effective, policies aimed at limiting resource extraction, redirecting rents, or demand saturation must be widely accepted by the public, which largely depends on strong environmental preferences. This highlights the key role of political economy considerations, behavioral interventions, and more broadly, the importance of fostering awareness.

Third, our conditions closely align with the concept of sufficiency. Avoiding rebound effects requires robust environmental preferences. Demand saturation through consumption restrictions represents a sufficiency strategy in itself. While the concepts of circular economy and sufficiency are often examined separately, our research bridges them by demonstrating that sufficiency is a necessary condition for circularity to result in resource mitigation.

By providing insights into the conditions supporting climate mitigation through circular economy practices, our framework also highlights fruitful avenues for future research. In particular, our framework is qualitative in nature because it needs to inform a large number of very different models. Future research should strive to improve the quantification of the effects we identified and of the associated resource savings and rebounds, which vary widely by sector and by country. Moreover, quantification will reveal the degree of stringency necessary in implementing these conditions and policies. In addition, future research should explore the robustness of our results by relaxing the key hypotheses of our framework, such as the profitability of circular strategies or the absence of disruptive technical change. Finally, a key extension of this analysis is the exploration of natural monopoly resource markets where supply quantity is inversely related to price.

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APPENDIX

A Further Assumptions

We consider a global economy comprising a certain number of individuals who want to achieve a certain service/activity, which in turn provides them with a certain level of utility. We restrict our attention to market activities.

Resources are matter that was originally extracted from the ground, and that is used either as material support (recycled or not) or energy. *Materials* are defined as matter being used in the economy for service provision. Materials come from both virgin and recycled sources and include materials (re-)used within this period, and materials added to the stock, i.e., accumulated in buildings, infrastructure, and durable goods in use for more than one year (as in the terminology of Haas et al., 2020).

In this paper, we take into account the stock of materials only in its relationship to the flow: demand for maintenance or replacement, or recycled materials from the stock. We focus on material flows rather than stocks because we aim to study the links with climate mitigation, focusing on GHG flows. However, the separability of material stocks and flows is not easy, given that the stock requires a certain amount of materials and energy to be maintained and/or replaced, likely to increase with time (durability). *Energy* is the force that enables a certain level of activity. It is through energy that materials can be extracted and circulated, and stockpiles maintained. Hence, energy is an inherent part of the (final) service provided (substituting individuals' labor) and uses resources. Some resources are directly converted into energy, necessitating some material support. *Disposal* refers to materials that are returned to the environment in solid form or incinerated. Materials that are disposed of may come from material throughput or the destocking of stock materials. *Greenhouse gas emissions* refer to resources transformed into greenhouse gas emissions, interacting with the climate. Greenhouse gas emissions originate from the year's flow of resources, and possibly also from the flow of previously stored materials.

An important assumption underlying our framework is that all time/energy/monetary resources are used.⁴² For example, reuse can result in financial profits for the company, and these financial resources can be used to purchase new items whose production has a positive or negative ecological impact. The assumption that all resources are used implies that this new item would not be purchased otherwise. Similarly, changes in logistics or means of production imply a change in resource consumption, with impact reverberating down the value chain. All these transfers together can alter or enhance the outcomes at

⁴²Note that we focus on resources and abstract in this paper from considerations related to labor.

the macro level.⁴³

B Indirect Rebound: *re-spending*

Let us assume that consumers consume the circular product c in quantity C_c , which remains unchanged. This product amounts to the consumption of resources R_c . We assume that the circular strategy at the product level is consistent, meaning that it leads to $\Delta R_c < 0$. Note that this assumption is challenged in Section 3.3.

If the price of c decreases, consumers have a surplus of budget to allocate to other consumptions s : $\Delta C_s > 0$. This additional consumption is equivalent to consuming $\Delta R_s > 0$.

Therefore, overall resource use can still decrease if the reduction in resources from product c (ΔR_c) is greater than the increase from additional consumption (ΔR_s); that is, if the consumer's basket composition is sufficiently resource-efficient.

Note that since this effect does not account for substitution, it assumes that the resource savings from the circular strategy are significant and that the consumer's consumption basket was already low-resource-intensive.

C Substitution Effect *versus* Direct Rebound

In the case of the direct rebound, consumers react to the decreased price of c by increasing the consumption of the product c : $\Delta C_c > 0$. If c competes with a resource-intensive good s , there can be a further increase in the consumption of c , through a substitution effect, such that $\Delta C'_c > 0$ and $\Delta C_s < 0$. Hence, the resource accounting gives:

$$\Delta R_c + \Delta R'_c + \Delta R_s \tag{1}$$

Resource mitigation requires that:

$$|\Delta R_c + \Delta R'_c| < |\Delta R_s| \tag{2}$$

Resource mitigation can still occur if the (partially) replaced good is specifically very resource-intensive.

⁴³Not making this assumption would mean omitting the secondary effects of circular practices and focusing solely on the direct effect (e.g, waste avoided by reuse), and therefore not being able to examine the macro-economic impact.